

INTERACTION BETWEEN CARBON FIBRE AND THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The interaction between carbon fibre and thermoplastics (low density polyethylene, polyethylene terephthalate, and polyetheretherketone) were investigated by means of differential scanning calorimetry and hot stage polarizing microscopy. The results obtained from differential scanning calorimetry show that a higher remelting temperature delayed the crystallization behaviour. The same results occurred at a longer remelted holding time and a rapid cooling rate. The morphology of thermoplastic polymer with carbon fibre was observed during the process. A transcrystalline structure formed around the fibre under suitable crystallization conditions. A simple method for a well developed transcrystalline layer around the fibre based on the differential scanning calorimetry combined with the hot stage polarizing microscopy was built up.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mechanical properties of a fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite is primarily dependent on three factors : (1) strength and modulus of the fibre, (2) strength and chemical stability of the matrix, and (3) effectiveness of the bond between matrix and fibre in transferring stress across the interface. By setting up suitable thermal gradients in a polymer melt or in contact with a surface acting as a nucleating substrate, it is possible to produce orientation by means of the crystallization process [1], which produces folded chain lamellae oriented perpendicular to the original line or sheet [2]. In a sense, all crystal growth is epitaxial, since new layers are deposited in perfect register on the growth surface of the previously grown crystal [3]. In the case of macromolecules, a special situation arises when an extended chain crystal serves as a substrate for crystallization. If a fibre is wetted by the crystallable polymer, the surface of the fibre can serve as a heterogeneous nucleus. The presence of a wettable surface can cause oriented overgrowth or epitaxy in crystallizing macromolecules. The epitaxy was first reported by Jenckel et al [4]. Transcrystalline growth has been observed to take place for many fibre-polymer systems [5-9]. Although there are numerous studies concerned with transcrystallization, the role of processing conditions on transcrystallization in fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymer is not fully understood. The objective of this work was to establish suitable conditions for transcrystallization on fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymer.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

Hercules AS-4 carbon fibre, obtained from APC-2 prepreg dissolved in α -chloronaphthalene at 230°C [10], was used as a reinforcement. Low density polyethylene (PE), M801, supplied by Monsanto Ltd., polyethylene terephthalate (PET), B90N, supplied by ICI PLC, polyetheretherketone (PEEK) supplied by ICI PLC were used as matrices. The peak (T_{mp}) and end (T_{me}) temperatures of the melting endotherm and the onset (T_{co}) and peak (T_{cp}) temperatures of the crystallization exotherm of the matrix materials are listed in Table 1. The thermal analysis was used by a Perkin Elmer DSC-2. The equilibrium temperatures (T_e) were collected elsewhere [11,12].

Table 1. The peak (T_{mp}) and end (T_{me}) temperatures of the melting endotherms, equilibrium temperatures (T_e), and the onset (T_{co}) and peak (T_{cp}) temperatures of the crystallization exotherms of matrix materials. Heating rate : 20°C/min, remelting temperature (T_r), and cooling rate : 40°C/min.

Materials	T_{mp} (°C)	T_{me} (°C)	T_e (°C)	T_r (°C)	T_{co} (°C)	T_{cp} (°C)
PE	110	136	142	150	99	88
PET	260	271	280 ^a	300	193	152
PEEK	340	362	395 ^b	400	292	277

a. Data from Wunderlich (1980)

b. Data from Blundell (1983)

2.2 CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES

A Perkin Elmer DSC-2 differential scanning calorimeter (calibrated using In and Pb) was utilized for the melting and crystallization behaviour of materials. Sample mass was of 8 to 10 mg. The heating rate was 20°C/min. The morphology of matrix polymer with carbon fibre was observed using a hot stage polarizing microscope (HSPM) during the process. A Leitz Laborlux 12 pol S polarized microscope with Linkam THMS 600 hot stage (calibrated using In and Pb) was used here.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY

In order to investigate the effect of remelting temperature (T_r) on the crystallization behaviour of fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymer, polyetheretherketone (PEEK) with AS-4 carbon fibre (CF/PEEK) was studied first in this work. The remelting temperatures were set at two different temperatures. One was at 380°C below the equilibrium temperature (at 395°C) of PEEK. Another one was at 400°C above the equilibrium temperature. The remelted holding times were set for 0 min, 3min, 5min, 10min, 15min, and 20min. The onset (T_{co}) and peak (T_{cp}) temperatures of the crystallization exotherm are shown in Table 2. The values of T_{co} and T_{cp} of CF/PEEK decrease with a longer remelted holding time. When the remelted holding time set from 380°C up to 400°C, the T_{co} and T_{cp} of crystallization exotherm decreased. It could explain that the melt was taken to successively higher temperatures and held the polymer for longer holding times at temperatures well above its melting point, and the previous nucleation agents were destroyed more.

The effect of cooling rate was then studied at the remelting temperature of 400°C. After remelting at 400°C, CF/PEEK cooled to room temperature at cooling rates of 20°C/min, 40°C/min, and 80°C/min. The results are shown in Table 3. An increase of cooling rate resulted to decrease of the values of T_{co} and T_{cp} .

Table 2. The onset (T_{co}) and peak (T_{cp}) temperatures of the crystallization exotherm of CF/PEEK at remelting temperatures (T_r), 380°C and 400°C, respectively. Cooling rate : 20°C/min.

(a) T_r at 380°C			(b) T_r at 400°C		
$T_{rt}(\text{min})$	$T_{co}(^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{cp}(^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{rt}(\text{min})$	$T_{co}(^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{cp}(^{\circ}\text{C})$
1	299	286	1	299	286
3	300	288	3	299	284
5	300	288	5	299	284
10	298	288	10	297	283
15	299	287	15	294	282
20	298	285	20	292	278

Table 3. Effect of cooling rate on the crystallization behaviour of CF/PEEK. Remelting temperature : 400°C. Symbols refer to Table 2.

Cooling rate ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)	$T_{co}(^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{cp}(^{\circ}\text{C})$
20	298	286
40	292	277
80	280	263

3.2 POLARIZED-LIGHT MICORSCOPY

For the observation of crystal growth, a specimen was prepared by a single carbon fibre placed between two thin films of PEEK. The specimen placed between two glass slides was set at a hot stage polarized microscope. A continuous stream of nitrogen was introduced on the hot stage during the process. After the process, the thickness of the specimen is about 0.04 mm. The specimens were heated to two different remelting temperatures, 380°C and 400°C, at a heating rate of 20°C/min, then holding at remelting temperature for 10min. An isothermal crystallization was taken at 270°C. The cooling rate between remelting temperatures and isothermal crystallization temperature was at 20°C/min. Spherulites grown in PEEK were observed. The spherulites formed at 380°C remelting temperature were more than those formed at 400°C remelting temperature (see Figure 1). Photographs show that the melt was taken to successively higher temperatures before crystallization, and the number of nuclei decreased and spherulites grew well.

Figure 1. Morphology of spherulites in PEEK matrix at 270°C isothermal crystallization. Photographs were taken at isothermal crystallization for 2 minutes. (a) Remelting temperature at 380°C; (b) remelting temperature at 400°C. Cooling rate was at 20°C/min.

The effects of isothermal crystallization temperature (T_i) and cooling rate on the crystallization behaviour were investigated. Specimens were prepared at the remelting temperatures of 380°C and 400°C for 10 minutes, then cooled to 280°C , 290°C , and 300°C for isothermal crystallization (below and higher than the peak temperature of crystallization exotherm). The cooling rates between remelting temperatures and isothermal crystallization temperatures were at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The morphology of CF/PEEK at different isothermal crystallization conditions are shown in Figure 2. The photographs were taken at isothermal crystallization for 2 minutes. Photographs show that the number of nuclei was highly dependent on the effects of isothermal crystallization temperature and cooling rate. An increase of isothermal crystallization temperature resulted in a decrease of isolate spherulites (see Figure 1b and 2c, 2b and 2d). The same result occurred when an increase of cooling rate reduced the number of isolate spherulite (see Figure 1a and 2a, 1b and 2b, 2c and 2d). No isolate spherulite was found when the isothermal crystallization temperatures were set up higher than 290°C for 2 minutes.

Figure 2. Morphology of CF/PEEK at different isothermal crystallization conditions. (a) Remelting temperature at 380°C for 10minutes, then cooling to 270°C at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. (b) Remelting temperature at 400°C for 10minutes, then cooling to 270°C at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. (c) Remelting temperature at 400°C for 10minutes, then cooling to 280°C at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. (d) Remelting temperature at 400°C for 10minutes, then cooling to 280°C at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Photographs were taken at isothermal crystallization for 2 minutes.

An isothermal crystallization temperature was set at 300°C for 40 minutes (cooling rate at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$), a transcrystalline layer around the fibre was observed (see Figure 3). The transcrystalline layer around the fibre and some large spherulites grew well after isothermal crystallization for 110 minutes.

Figure 3. Morphology of carbon fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone. Photographs were taken at (a) remelting temperature at 400°C for 10 minutes, then isothermal crystallization at 300°C for 110 minutes, and (b) after isothermal crystallization for 110 minutes, then cooled down to room temperature. Cooling rate was at 40°C/min.

3.3 EFFECT OF FIBRE ON CRYSTALLIZATION OF POLYETHYLENE AND POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE

The investigation described above shows that it is possible to grow a well developed transcrystalline layer of PEEK on AS-4 carbon fibre under suitable conditions. In understanding whether this also applies to other crystallable polymers, the matrix materials, low density polyethylene (PE) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET), were used here.

The experience gained from CF/PEEK showed that a remelting temperature higher than equilibrium temperature, and a rapid cooling rate from a melt to an isothermal crystallization temperature, which was slightly above the temperature of the peak of the crystallization exotherm was conducive to the formation of the transcrystalline layer. Thus, the conditions obtained of CF/PEEK and CF/PET from DSC experiments are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 The processing conditions for CF/PE and CF/PET. Heating rate : 20°C/min, remelting temperature T_r , remelting time : 10min, cooling rate : 40°C/min, isothermal crystallization temperature : T_c .

Material	T_r (°C)	T_c (°C)
CF/PE	160	103
CF/PET	300	205

The effect of carbon fibre on polyethylene and polyethylene terephthalene polymers was observed on the hot stage polarized microscope. Under the above conditions the transcrystalline layers around the fibre were observed (see Figure 4). Thus, the procedure established from CF/PEEK can be applied successfully to other matrix materials.

Figure 4. Morphology of transcrystalline structure in (a) CF/PE and (b) CF/PET.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The crystallization behaviour of thermoplastics is strongly affected by carbon fibre.
2. Under suitable conditions, the fibre induced the formation of a well developed transcrystalline layer.
3. A simple approach has been developed for identification of the conditions required for the formation of a well developed transcrystalline layer around the fibre.

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